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IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SENSE OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ON THE BASIS OF PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH

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Annotation: This article covers the theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogical approaches aimed at forming and developing students' sense of social responsibility in the modern educational process. The content and essence of the concept of social responsibility, its importance in personal and social development are analyzed in depth. Also, the mechanisms of forming civic duty, responsibility to society, environmental and moral responsibility in the minds of students are considered within the framework of pedagogical approaches.

Keywords: Pedagogical approach, student personality, methodological improvement, civic education, competence, moral education.

Introduction.

In modern society, not only professional qualifications of a person, but also his social responsibility, civic position and sense of duty to society are becoming an important factor. Social responsibility is an awareness of the impact of a person's actions and decisions on society, a willingness to act in the interests of the common good and a conscious attitude towards fulfilling one's obligations. This is especially relevant for the younger generation of students studying in educational institutions. After all, today's student is the leader of tomorrow, the driving force of social development. Therefore, the formation of a sense of social responsibility in their minds is one of the strategic tasks of pedagogical activity.

Various forms of pedagogical approaches serve as an important tool in developing personal and social competencies in students. In particular, through person-oriented, competency-based and activity-oriented approaches, it is possible to awaken the social consciousness of students and teach them to make responsible decisions before society. Such approaches, taking into account the individual characteristics of the student, his internal motivation, his attitude towards social values, encourage him to learn through real-life activities. This, in turn, contributes to his personal growth and the formation of a socially mature person. The education system, as an institution that not only provides knowledge, but also performs a social educational function, plays a key role in the formation of a socially responsible person. By promoting moral values among students,

instilling a spirit of social activism, patriotism, and not being indifferent to environmental and social problems, we can strengthen the foundations of a healthy, responsible society.

Methodology.

Any scientific research work is strengthened by its theoretical and principled foundations, scientific approaches, and methodological tools. In this study, the improvement of the methodology aimed at developing a sense of social responsibility in students was carried out on the basis of pedagogical approaches, which were based on the following main methodological principles: a person-centered approach, an activity-centered approach, a competency-based approach, and a systematic approach. First of all, the person-centered approach places the student at the center of the pedagogical process. This approach takes into account the social experience, spiritual and moral outlook and personal needs of each student. During the study, analyzing how the sense of social responsibility is formed and strengthened in the student's personality, special attention was paid to creating a pedagogical environment based on this approach that encourages student activity and allows him to express his point of view. Also, based on the activity-oriented approach, a sense of responsibility was formed by involving students in social practice. Through this approach, the student is not a passive listener, but an active participant in the learning process. Through participation in social projects, solving problem situations, group discussions, role-playing games and practical assignments, students were directed to feel and understand their responsibility in social relations.

The competency-based approach used in the study, in turn, provided for the formation of social, moral and civic competencies in students. Based on this approach, the concept of social responsibility was interpreted in an integrated manner with the professional, communicative and cultural competencies of the student. As a result, during the learning process, students not only acquired theoretical knowledge, but also learned to apply it in real-life situations. In addition, all components of pedagogical activity - goal, content, form, means and results - were designed in harmony with each other on the basis of a systematic approach. This made it possible to clearly plan measures to develop social responsibility in students and assess their effectiveness. As research methods, observation, questionnaires, interviews, experimental work, diagnostic tests and pedagogical monitoring tools were used. Through these methods, the dynamics of the formation of a sense of social responsibility were identified, and the effectiveness of the new methodology was evaluated on a scientific basis. In general, through the application of methodological foundations in such a

systematic approach, a stable formation of social responsibility in the minds of students, strengthening their social activity and civic position were achieved. This fully corresponds to such important criteria of the pedagogical process as humanity, innovation and effectiveness.

Literature analysis (review):

Scientific and pedagogical views on the formation and development of a sense of social responsibility in students have been widely discussed in recent years as one of the pressing issues facing the modern education system. Literature analysis shows that the concept of social responsibility has been studied within the framework of various disciplines - pedagogy, psychology, sociology, philosophy and even ecology, and each approach has highlighted its own specific aspects of this concept.

In pedagogical literature, social responsibility is often considered inextricably linked with the concepts of civic education, moral maturity and social activity. For example, N. Z. Gulomov[3; 256], A. Yuldoshev[6; Local pedagogical scientists such as [198] emphasize the important role of the education system in educating the younger generation as socially active, conscious and responsible individuals. They argue that the social responsibility of a student begins, first of all, with an understanding of his place in society, and this process is carried out through pedagogical guidance, active methods and a moral and cultural environment.

In foreign literature, this issue has been studied through more systematic approaches. In particular, the principles of critical pedagogy, social justice and human rights-based education put forward by the educator P. Freire[1; 183] are evaluated as effective methodologies that serve to instill social consciousness and a sense of responsibility in students. In sociological sources, social responsibility is interpreted in a broader social context. Sociologists such as R. Merton[4; 702] and A. Giddens[2; 1048] have studied the influence of social institutions, cultural environment and social roles on personal responsibility. According to their views, family upbringing, social peer group and mass media play an important role in the formation of a sense of responsibility. At the same time, it is argued that as individualism increases among young people, the need to involve them in social obligations is increasing.

In the psychological literature, the formation of a sense of responsibility is associated with personal qualities, motivation and emotional-intellectual growth. According to the social learning theory put forward by A. Bandura[5; 320], people are influenced by the actions and attitudes of others. This indicates the importance of the teacher's personality, the learning environment and the

opportunities for sharing experience in the formation of social responsibility in students. As can be seen from the literature review, the formation of a sense of social responsibility in students is a multifactorial and multifaceted process, and an integrated approach is necessary for its development. Therefore, the article used a synthesis of pedagogical and psychological approaches as a theoretical basis, and an improved methodology was developed based on innovative methods suitable for modern education.

Discussion and analysis:

The modern education system requires students not only to form knowledge and skills, but also to mature into personal, moral and socially mature people. Instilling a sense of social responsibility, especially in the younger generation, and transforming them into individuals who understand their duty and responsibility to society and have an active civic position, is one of the most urgent directions of modern pedagogical activity.

Observations and experimental tests conducted within the framework of this study showed that traditional educational approaches do not fully serve the consistent and sustainable formation of social responsibility in students. For example, in an educational process based solely on lectures and focused on mastery, the student does not encounter real social problems in society, which slows down the formation of the experience of making responsible decisions in his mind. Therefore, methods based on activity, cooperation and independent thinking have been proven to be more effective in forming social consciousness. The essence of the methodology developed on the basis of pedagogical approaches is that by designing the educational process based on the student's personal experience, life interests and spiritual values, the opportunity is created to educate them as active social subjects. This methodology uses role-playing, social projects, debates, and problem-based assignments to guide students in finding solutions to real-world social issues. Through such approaches, students not only learn to make responsible decisions, but also gain a deeper understanding of how their actions and choices can impact society.

As a result of experimental tests, it was found that the level of development of social responsibility in students is directly related to the level of their involvement in the educational process. When interactive, innovative and life-oriented forms of education (for example, social service projects, volunteering, debates) are used instead of centrally controlled and standard-based forms of education, the student's social activity and sense of responsibility increase significantly. Another important aspect is that the development of social responsibility depends not only on academic subjects, but also on the general

spiritual and moral environment of the educational institution. In this environment, values such as justice, equality, solidarity, social assistance, and environmental awareness should be prioritized. Also, the ability of the teacher to be an example and to establish friendly and open communication with students directly affects the formation of a sense of responsibility. The methodology developed on the basis of pedagogical approaches, its essence and practical application can achieve high efficiency in the formation of social responsibility in students. The coordinated use of approaches in this process - especially person-oriented and activity-based approaches - allows the formation of the student's personality as a socially active, conscious and responsible subject.

Conclusion.

The formation and development of a sense of social responsibility in the younger generation is one of the priority tasks of the modern education system. The conducted scientific and pedagogical analyzes, observations and experimental tests have shown that in achieving this goal, along with traditional educational methods, the introduction of innovative methodologies based on pedagogical approaches is highly effective. In particular, the methodological model developed on the basis of person-oriented, activity-based and competency-based approaches serves to develop students' personal activity, independent thinking, and a deep understanding of their duty and responsibility to society.

When the educational process is combined with the personal experience, life needs and social values of students through pedagogical approaches, conditions are created for their formation of social consciousness and maturation as responsible citizens. The main advantage of the methodology is that it is not limited to theoretical knowledge, but prepares the student for life through practical activities, social projects, and analysis of problem situations. In this regard, the results of this study serve to socialize pedagogical activity, strengthen civic education, and create a socially responsible environment in higher educational institutions. In the future, by more widely introducing the recommendations developed on the basis of these methodological approaches into pedagogical practice, significant positive results can be achieved in the education of the younger generation.

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